

Research and Innovation Action

CESSDA Strengthening and Widening

Project Number: 674939

Start Date of Project: 01/08/2015

Duration: 24 months

Deliverable 2.3

Title Stakeholder workshop Report 1

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	30/04/16
Actual Submission Date	29/06/16
Justification for delivery delay	See introduction page 7
Work Package	WP 2
Task	2.3
Type	Report
EC Approval Status	7 September 2016
Version	V2.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.24
<p>Abstract: Report on the “Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking” workshop held in The Hague Netherlands on June 15th and 16th, 2016 (instead of April 2016, as originally scheduled) in respect with the organizational process behind the setup of this workshop as well as the outcomes of this preparation, and outline of all sessions during 2 days.</p>	
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History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
1.0	09/06/2016	1st draft by the Task Leader	Nathalie Paton
1.1	09/06/2016	1st Review by the WP Leader - WP2	Jean-Baptiste Milon
1.2	13/06/2016	2nd draft by the Task Leader	Nathalie Paton
	16-17/06/2016	Workshop	
1.3	17/06/2016	3rd draft by the Task leader	Jean-Baptiste Milon
1.4	20/06/2016	Review by the WP Leader - WP2	Jean-Baptiste Milon
1.5	23/06/2016	Review by the Project Coordinator	Ivana Ilijasic Versic
1.6	24/06/2016	Review by the WP Leader - WP2	Jean-Baptiste Milon
1.7	27/06/2016	Review by the Chair of the Delivery Committee	Jindrich Krejci
1.8	28/06/2016	Review by WP leader - WP4	Marion Wittenberg
1.9	29/06/2016	Review by the WP Leader - WP2	Jean-Baptiste
1.9	29/06/2016	Review by the Project Coordinator	Ivana Ilijasic Versic
2.0	29/06/2016	Submission by the Project Coordinator	Ivana Ilijasic Versic

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Time Schedule before Delivery

Next Action	Deadline	Delivery leader
1st Draft version finalized	13/06/2016	CNRS - Nathalie Paton
Workshop 1	16-17/06/2016	
2nd draft finalised	17/06/2016	CNRS - Nathalie Paton
Review by the WP leader	24/06/2016	CESSDA - Jean-Baptiste Milon
Review by the Chair of the Delivery Committee	27/06/2016	CSDA - Jindrich Krejci
Review by WP leader WP4	28/06/2016	DANS - Marion Wittenberg
Review by the Project Coordinator	28/06/2016	CESSDA - Ivana Ilijasic Versic
Approval and Submission by the Project Coordinator to the European Commission	29/06/2016	CESSDA - Ivana Ilijasic Versic

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The CESSDA-SaW H2020 project aims at achieving full European coverage; the widened membership must form a strong network where global best practice is built into the infrastructure of European social science and research. In order to reach this goal, a series of workshops and a final dissemination event are being organised throughout the two-year project.

This deliverable reports on the process of organising workshops in general and discusses the outcome of this preparation in respect to workshop 1 (WS1). Hosted and primarily organised by DANS, the “Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking” workshop took place at The Hague on June 16th and June 17th 2016. It aimed mainly for the technical staff of Service Providers (SP) in order to assist them in obtaining the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) certification. Other topics, addressed during the event, cover areas promoting partnerships with CESSDA non-member countries’ archives, prospecting sustainability opportunities through support services, and testing a cost/benefit advocacy programme.

The first part of this deliverable is related to the work completed before starting the organisation of workshops mentioned in the Description of Action (DoA). The delay in hosting events in the SaW project is explained in relationship to the numerous issues contained in the Grant agreement (GA) and the commitment of all partners involved in the SaW project to offer the best possible service to potential attendees of events. The presentation of the organisational process of workshops is followed by a second part in which the content and attendance of WS1 are addressed. This section of the deliverable starts off by giving insight on the aim, the target audience and the topics of the two-day event.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

LOD	Linked Open Data
DoA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
WS	Workshop
SP	Service Provider
WP	Work-Package
CESSDA	Consortium Of European Social Sciences Data Archives
CESSDA AS	CESSDA Aksjeselskap
CESSDA MO	CESSDA Main Office
CESSDA SPs	CESSDA Service Providers
DSA	Data Seal of Approval
Progedo	Production et gestion des données
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CSDA	Institute of Sociology of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic
DANS	DANS / Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen
DDA	Danish National Archive - Danish Data Archive
DoW	Description of Work
EKKE	Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon
FFZG	Sveuciliste u Zagrebu Filozofski Fakultet
FORS	Swiss Foundation for Research in the Social Sciences
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
GESIS	GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
ICSULISBOA	Instituto De Ciencias Da Universidade De Lisboa
IEN	Institut Ekonomskih Nauka
ISSDA	Irish Social Science Data Archive, University College Dublin
KSP	Knowledge-Sharing Platform
LIDA	Lietuvos HSM duomenų archyvas
NSD	Norsk samfunnsvitenskapelig datatjeneste AS
RODA	Arhiva Română de Date Sociale
SND	University of Gothenburg - Swedish National Data Service
SOHDA	Social Sciences and Humanities Data Archive
SU SAV	Sociologický ústav Slovenskej akadémie vied
TARKI	Tarki Foundation
UTARTU	Tartu Ülikool
UKDA	United Kingdom Data Service
UniData	Centre UniData – Bicocca Data Archive

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. GOAL OF TASK & DELIVERABLE 2.3

The objective of task 2.3, as defined by the Description of Action of the Grant Agreement, consists of monitoring the organisation of a dissemination event and at least three stakeholder workshops; other workshops and smaller events are mentioned as a possibility. Coordination by T2.3 is meant to prevent overlapping of programmes, over-solicitation of the same target audiences, general management of budget, coordination between partners involved in organization, and logistic solutions. The objective of this report is twofold: first to give a general description of the organising process for workshops and events, and secondly to report on the first workshop organised within the SaW project.

Task 2.3 helps organizers to manage and set-up in a timely manner four different workshops and one final dissemination event. These events are scheduled in months 11, 15, 20, 22 and 23. CNRS (Progedo), also provides logistic support for the registration process, travel arrangements and accommodation of attendees for events.

The 1st workshop of CESSDA-SaW entitled “Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking” took place on Thursday 16 and Friday 17 of June 2016 in Den Haag, The Netherlands. This report consists of two parts: the organizational process behind the setup of the workshop (WS) is explained in the first part. Secondly, a general description of workshop 1 (WS1) is offered by examining the aim, the target audience and the topics of the workshop, before considering the outcomes of the event in terms of Service Providers’ (SPs) attendance (number of invitations against the show-up rate), distribution among countries of attendees, level of staff, etc. However, two other deliverables, D4.1 and D4.4, provide an in-depth analysis of this workshop, therefore in D2.3 the main focus relates to the process of organising the WS, with just a brief summary of its content.

1.2. JUSTIFICATION FOR THE DELIVERY DELAY

Several issues had to be dealt with before setting up any event. Many contradictions in the DoA (the timeline, the number and size of events, funds available, the description in T2.3 in comparison to other tasks), prevented a quick progress. To ensure the delivery of high quality events fully representing the stakes of the SaW project, a lengthy process took place.

Ultimately, this delay allowed the management team to allocate the responsibilities and funding among the task partners. This affected the initial timeline set out in the grant agreement (GA), postponing WS1 from April to June 2016. It also led to the creation of collaborative tools designed at addressing organisational issues. Setting a new timing for the first workshop allowed interconnection of work in four different tasks within the project with respect to existing dependencies. It also contributed to the multiple objectives and brought efficiency in both organisation of planned events, and organisation of work in the project.

In addition, the timing was set up optimally in respect to the timing of other events relevant to the target groups (e.g. IASSIST Conference, meetings of different CESSDA bodies, etc.).

2. SET UP OF WORKSHOPS IN THE SAW PROJECT

2.1. BACKGROUND: ISSUES IN NEED OF COORDINATION BETWEEN TASKS IN WP2-3-4

Task 2.3 is part of the Work Package 2 “Communication and Dissemination” and its main aim is to manage organisation of workshops mentioned in different sections of the Work Packages 3 (WP3) and 4 (WP4). However, given the number of issues that quickly arose once the project began, these issues are briefly stated, including the way in which they were addressed, in order to provide insight on the actual layout of workshops and tailoring of WS1 throughout this process.

- Workshops listed in the GA

One of the first issues encountered at the beginning of the project was the number and the schedule of events originally listed in the DoA throughout the project duration. This table shows an overall breakdown of months listed in DoA related to a potential event.

Table 1: Original Events Schedule

<p>Events listed in Month 6</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T2.3 (D2.3) – Stakeholder workshop on national data archives ➤ T4.4 (MS21) – Workshop to bring the demand information together ➤ T4.4 (MS23)– Collaborative workshop on establishing partnerships between CESSDA and service providers (Reported in D4.8, M24) ➤ T4.5 (MS23)– Collaborative workshop on establishing partnerships between CESSDA and service providers; referenced in the 1st period administrative report ➤ T4.6 – Workshop could be session within another workshop
<p>Month 12</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T2.3 (D2.4) - Workshop on discovery of the state-of-the-art, infrastructure requirements and other related topics
<p>Month 16</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T4.1 (MS17, D4.1) – First workshop on Guidelines for CESSDA members on DSA certification
<p>Month 18</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T2.3 (D2.5) – Workshop on construction of development packages and other topics if necessary ➤ T4.1 (D4.2)– Integration workshop ➤ T4.4 (MS25)– Collaborative workshop on establishing partnerships between CESSDA and service providers (Reported in D4.8, M24) ➤ T4.5 (MS25)– workshop on the processes of integration of data services into CESSDA; public URL on the CESSDA SaW project website ➤ T4.6 (D4.9) - Case studies and focus groups of costs/benefits
<p>Month 20</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T4.1 (MS18, D4.1) – Second workshop on Guidelines for CESSDA members on DSA certification
<p>Month 21</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T2.3 final conference/dissemination event; D2.6 Dissemination event report in Month 22
<p>Other events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ T3.2 Audit of current status of data archives in all ERA countries: Possibility of organizing a workshop will be explored and potentially used for collecting additional information.” ➤ T3.4 Strengthening and widening through expanding data perimeter: Possibility of organizing a series of workshops with the ambition of bridging the gap between the different stakeholders at country/regional/European levels and discussing the different models and paths for development

As it clearly appears hereinabove, events were stretched out over fifteen months, from month 6 to month 21 and were meant to take place in six different months, with a first event held as early as in month 6.

With later re-scheduling, all workshops take place in 4 months of the SaW project: months 11, 15, 20 and 22.

- Budgetary issues

An overall budget of €80.000,00 was allocated under T2.3 on the basis of €800,00 per travel, summing up to the equivalent of 100 travels. Budget was originally allocated to CESSDA AS although activities remained listed under CNRS' tasks. In respect to this matter, €80.000,00 were reallocated to CNRS as part of the amendment request that was adopted by the EC on 12 February 2016, stating the transfer of money from CESSDA AS to CNRS under the "other costs" category for Task 2.3. Based on the funds available for organising workshops by CNRS, it was agreed that partners could invite 30 participants for each of the 3 workshops and the final dissemination event, while the remaining funds are distributed to support venue and catering costs for each event.

- Procedures and contacts for the SaW project

Some of the WS described in the DoA as well as the final dissemination event require inviting stakeholders' representatives at different levels (SPs' staff, contacts at ministerial level, officials from the EC and/or high level representatives) in both CESSDA and non CESSDA member countries. It was suggested that a contact list should be set up along with general procedures. The contact list would contain targeted institutions, contact persons, possible representatives, and any other information that could be used for the invitations. The general procedures would provide guidelines on how to contact different representatives following different scenarios. The document was created and edited by FORS.

2.2. DISTRIBUTION OF EVENTS

During the 2nd consortium meeting of the SaW project held in Bergen on 24-25 February 2016 it was decided to hold 4 workshops and one final dissemination event. New distribution of events brought both higher cost efficiency, and more efficiency in achieving continuity of work. Below are the details of these 5 events:

Table 2: Distribution of Events

Workshop on Archives 1st workshop on DSA guidelines	D2.3 (T2.3) report 1 + MS21 (T4.4) Bring the demand information together + D4.1 (T4.1) Trust workshop (M12) + MS17 (T4.3) (ex MS4.8): Guidelines for CESSDA members on DSA certification + T4.6
Collaborative Workshop WS on Establishing partnerships	D2.4 report 2 (T2.3)+ MS23 (T4.5 1st workshop) Collaborative workshops Establishing partnerships between CESSDA & SP + T4.6 + WP3 (T3.2 Audit of current status of data archives in all ERA countries + T3.4 Strengthening and widening through expanding data perimeter)
Integration workshop 2nd workshop on DSA guidelines	D2.5 report 3 + D4.2 (T4.1): integration + MS18 (ex MS4.9) (T4.3) trust
Processes of integration workshop WS on data services provided by CESSDA	MS 25 (ex MS4.16) (T4.5 2nd workshop) + WP3 (T3.2 Audit of current status of data archives in all ERA countries + T3.4 Strengthening and widening through expanding data perimeter)
Final Dissemination event High visibility & high impact event	D2.6 Bringing together stakeholders of social sciences data infrastructures + focus on the user experience of searching for data

Workshops are organized around milestones and deliverables, as well as target audiences. In the diagram below both organisational partners and the timeline of events are highlighted.

Figure 1: Workshops and Final Event Planning

The first series of workshops (WS1 and WS3) have more technical approach; they are meant to strengthen techniques and practices of CESSDA member countries' Service Providers and archives in aspiring member countries. The second series of workshops (WS2 and WS4) have a policy approach and are intended to widen the perimeter of the consortium by meeting with aspiring member countries' representatives. The second series of workshops showcases the best practices of large SPs, highlights models for sustainability, promotes archiving services and funding opportunities.

Workshop 1 and workshop 3, held respectively in month 11 and month 19, aim at technical staff of Service Providers and organises trainings on guidelines for Data Seal of Approval. Additional sessions aiming at collecting information for audit of services and needs, can be added to these events. Workshop 2 and 4, held respectively in month 15 and month 22, are stakeholders' workshops aiming at high level and officials from ministries, research councils, funding agencies, service providers and universities.

WS1 and WS3 organisations are primarily managed by DANS, while WS2 and WS4 are primarily organised by TARKI Foundation. The final event is CNRS' responsibility. Even though specific partners are organising the event, the organisational process brings together the lead partners (DANS, TARKI, NSD), the task leaders involved in the sessions, the Project Manager and CNRS.

2.3. COORDINATION TOOLS

Online collaborative tools are meant to help setting up, organising, foreseeing and/or monitoring workloads for workshops (i.e. coordination stakeholder workshop document; detailed workshop plan; workshop checklist; retroactive workshop calendars; registration form; accommodation procedures' note; etc.). Description of these tools is provided here: [Coordination of stakeholder workshop](#).

This online document was created for organisers of all CESSDA SaW events to help them plan the events in terms of participants (target audience, list of participants), content (programme of the workshop), while foreseeing logistic considerations (registration forms, rent of venue, catering, invoicing system, etc.).

Table 3: 1st Workshop Online Form

EVENT NAME	
1. Team responsible for the workshop	
2. Title of the workshop	
3. Tasks (within which it is organised):	
4. Description of workshop objectives	
5. Date and venue of the workshop	
6. Start month of preparation (Duration/ PM)	February
7. End month of preparation (Duration/ PM)	June 2016
8. Please describe the target audience to which the workshop is intended	
9. Provide a timeline for the organisation of the workshop describing the work plan and the distribution of responsibilities	
10. Present a detailed draft agenda of the workshop	
11. Deliverables & milestones of this workshop	

12. List of project partners involved in the organisation	
13. Describe and explain any other workshop related costs (Only non -core tas ks can be contracted out. E.g. catering, location, other services, etc.)	Cost (Euros)
1 Catering	
2 Keynote speaker	
3 Other invited external speakers (tbc)	
Total	
14. Total financing required (Euros) - (Sum of boxes 4, 7, 11 & 12)	

● Calendar, Detailed workshop plan and Checklist

A precise timeline was needed to establish deadlines for setting the agenda, venue, date, drafting and launching invitations, etc. all outlined in the [Detailed workshop plan](#) in order to keep schedule on track. [SaW workshop calendar](#) as well as [Workshop Checklist](#) were provided for monitoring actions done for WS1 and WS2; this timeline can be duplicated for latter events of the project.

Table 4: Workshop Checklist

Task	Duration	Start Date	End Date	Phase
Confirm place, date, venue	Month - 3,5	1 May 16	15 May 16	Workshop preparation phase
Finalize list of attendees	Month - 5	15 May 16	15 May 16	
Check attendees, send invitations & Form 1	Month - 4,5	29 May 16	15 Jun 16	Workshop preparation phase
Form 1 relance	Form 1 + 1 week	5 Jun 16	12 Jun 16	
Receive responses to Form 1	Form 1 + 2 weeks	12 Jun 16	26 Jun 16	Workshop preparation phase
Send Form 2 to attendees	M-5 + 2 days	14 Jun 16	16 Jun 16	
Form 2 relance n°1	Form 2 + 1 week	21 Jun 16	28 Jun 16	Workshop preparation phase
Form 2 relance n°2	Form 2 + 2 weeks	28 Jun 16	12 Jul 16	
Contact attendees receive all Form 2	Week - 5	7 Sep 16	14 Sep 16	Workshop preparation phase
Attendee travel ticket booking	Week -1	8 Oct 16	15 Oct 16	
Workshop start date	Week 0	15 Oct 16	15 Oct 16	Workshop execution phase

This timeline serves to identify the following :

- What needs to be done before setting up workshops
- What needs to be completed during the workshops
- What the organisers need to handle after the completion of each workshop.

● Forms: Registration forms, travel forms, reimbursement of daily allowances form

Several documents were created for attendees to process registration: [Registration Form](#) , [How to book stays for workshops](#), and [Organisational matters to add to forms and rubrics online](#).

Figure 2: Online Registration form - Snapshot

cessda saw

Strengthening and widening the European infrastructure for social science data archives

CESSDA SaW Workshop - Widening the European infrastructure of social science data archives

19 & 20 October 2016, Budapest, Hungary

Please note that no information you will provide is disclosed.

*** Required**

Check the CESSDA-SaW webpage for information about the workshop here:
<http://cessdasaw.eu/2016/04/10/ws-2-budapest/>

Your first name *

Your answer

2.4. WEBSITE

In order for attendees to have access to a centralised platform with all the information related to the event and their stay, it was decided that the CESSDA website would host a page for each event¹.

Figure 3: CESSDA Website - Workshop Webpage - Snapshot

cessda
Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

Home / CESSDA Services / Resources / Events / CESSDA SaW Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking

CESSDA SaW Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking

Date: Thu 16 Jun 2016 09:00 - Fri 17 Jun 2016 15:00

CESSDA SaW stands for "Strengthening and Widening of the European infrastructure for social science data archives". The aim of the project is to achieve full European coverage; the widened membership must form a strong network where global best practice is built into the infrastructure of European social science and research.

Included in the activities foreseen within the project is the organisation of four workshops; two aimed at strengthening the network through knowledge exchange, and two geared towards widening the network via networking activities with national ministries, Research Councils, and the Social Sciences research community.

Welcome to the first CESSDA SaW workshop!

Please see the links on the left for more information and contact details.

Last updated: Tuesday 19 April 2016

Events

CESSDA SaW Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking

Home

Programme

Registration

Travel information

Location

Contact info

Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
 Anna van Saksenlaan 51
 2593 HW The Hague
 The Netherlands
 +31 70 349 44 50

¹ For WS1:

<http://cessda.net/CESSDA-Services/Resources/Events/CESSDA-SaW-Training-on-Trust-Identifying-Demand-Networking>

Once the CESSDA SaW website was up and running² the link to the website was added to invitations. In both cases, the page hosting the event contains information on the aim of the event, the programme, the registration process, travel & accommodation, location of the event (see example here below). The same information now appears on the CESSDA-SaW website :

Figure 4: CESSDA SaW Website - Workshop Webpage - Snapshot

Strengthening and Widening CESSDA

WS 1 – Workshop – The Hague NL – 16/06/2016

CESSDA SaW Training on Trust, Identifying Demand & Networking

Date: Thu 16 Jun 2016 09:00 – Fri 17 Jun 2016 15:00

WorkShop 1

CESSDA SaW Training
on Trust, Identifying
Demand & Networking

16-17 / 06 / 2016

WS 1 - Programme

WS 1 - Registration

² <http://cessdasaw.eu/2016/05/10/ws-1-the-hague/>

3. WORKSHOP 1 - TRAINING ON TRUST, IDENTIFYING DEMAND & NETWORKING

3.1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE WORKSHOP

3.1.1. AIM OF THE WORKSHOP

The workshop was focused around knowledge exchange between the current CESSDA Service Providers and social science data archives from aspiring countries, by offering training on Trust and guidelines to achieve a Data Seal of Approval (as required by the CESSDA Statutes in the Annex 2 Obligations). Strengthening between existing SPs and their mutual knowledge and experiences exchange was also encouraged, and four main objectives of this workshop (trust/demand/cost-benefit analysis/networking) formulated by four different Tasks were highly emphasised. Representatives of the different SPs were able to raise specific issues on the process for obtaining Data Seal of Approval (DSA), including comparison of procedures in the old version of guidelines and the new one. They were asked to share their preparation of documentation and evidence statements. In this respect, WS1 targeted high level staff from the SPs.

In addition to these goals, the event covered several related aspects of the CESSDA SaW project, in particular identification of support services needed and provided by CESSDA members, and testing of the requirements of cost/benefit advocacy programme. It also provided a framework for preparation of WS2.

3.1.2. TARGET AUDIENCE

WS1 was supposed to bring together individuals from CESSDA SaW beneficiaries and linked third parties (CESSDA SPs) and other aspiring archives, who have an overview of the technical needs of their institution and can follow through on implementing DSA certification. The target audience of this WS was therefore mainly composed of senior staff members.

When considering the level of coverage and potential attendees, all European Research Area countries (ERA) were initially considered. However, in the end the scope of potential countries was narrowed down to 37 countries:

Albania; Austria; Belarus; Belgium; Bosnia and Herzegovina; Bulgaria; Croatia; Czech Rep.; Denmark; Estonia; Finland; France; Germany; Greece; Hungary; Ireland; Italy; Kosovo; Latvia; Lithuania; Luxembourg; Macedonia; Montenegro; Netherlands; Norway; Poland; Portugal; Romania; Russia; Serbia; Slovakia; Slovenia; Spain; Sweden; Switzerland; Ukraine; United Kingdom.

Amongst these 37 countries, 11 countries could not be invited because no contact person had been identified:

Albania; Austria; Belarus; Bosnia and Herzegovina; Bulgaria; Luxembourg; Macedonia; Montenegro; Poland; Russia, Ukraine.

3.1.3. TOPICS

The WS was organised around several sessions that took place over the course of these two days. Since the main focus was the DSA training, the following topics were supported in the programme:

01. Trust: Training on how to achieve a Data Seal of Approval (DSA) (as required by the CESSDA Statutes in Annex 2 Obligations),

The first session was for all Service Providers. It focused on the important recent changes in the DSA guidelines. The DSA Seal will continue to exist, but its 16 assessment guidelines are changed into the “Common Requirements for Certification”. The consequences of this transition which are relevant for all SP’s, either already DSA-certified or not yet, were explained during this session.

The second session was on the DSA Self-Assessment test procedure for CESSDA SP's. This meeting targeted representatives of the SP's that still have to go through the certification process, preferably the participants who are - or have been - involved in the DSA certification process. As guidance for preparing the DSA procedure, the SP's were offered the possibility of a test self-assessment supervised and reviewed by DSA experts on site.

The third session explained the new "Common Requirements for Certification" in more detail for everyone concerned and/or interested.

02. Identifying demand for Support Services

CESSDA archives could perform supportive tasks for other archives, offering (technical) facilities and expertise on i.e. software, backup services and tools and archival policies. This session tried to identify the demand for such support services.

As part of the CESSDA SaW aspect of strengthening Service Providers (SPs) the coordination team investigated how SPs can support each other. As a growing consortium, CESSDA has considerable expertise and knowledge, but also services and tools that can be used to help other members of the community. The aim of this workshop was to find out what are Service Providers' expectations, and it was open for all of those who have a strategic understanding of current and future plans for the services a specific SP offers to a designated communities.

The half-day workshop presented support services to new and potential CESSDA Service Providers, discussed current SPs' strengths and weaknesses, looked for commonalities and finally finished with an in-depth discussion about possible solutions.

03. Focus group on costs/ benefit advocacy programme

An interactive session focusing on funding and cost-benefit advocacy toolkit being developed for the European CESSDA SaW project was conducted. It is expected that the toolkit will support the negotiation with ministries and funding organisations across Europe. The session was of interest to archives' staff with responsibility for bidding, funding and/or promotion and advocacy on behalf of the archive to the key stakeholders. Different countries at different levels on the development span of a social science data archive (none, new/emerging, mature) were welcomed.

04. Development of the non-member countries' collaboration network of Service Providers and planning the high-level Budapest meeting

First meeting of social science data archives outside of the current CESSDA consortium took place in the afternoon of the 1st day. It served as preparation for a high level workshop in Budapest on 19-20 October 2016.

This session had three main goals:

- 1 - Starting the development of a collaborative network;
- 2 - Collecting information on establishment of formal mechanisms of collaboration within wider CESSDA network;
- 3 - Collecting information on the expected collaborative mechanisms, based on a first set of suggestions introduced during the session, notably to find best solutions to identify stakeholders and strategies in order to integrate new members into CESSDA, or to build a close collaboration with CESSDA.

3.1.4. SESSIONS

Focus Group on Cost-Benefit Advocacy Program (T4.6)

This was an interactive focus group repeated over two parallel sessions. It was aimed at archive staff with responsibility for bidding for funding or promotion and advocacy of the archive to key stakeholders. We expect the cost-benefit advocacy toolkit under development to support the negotiation with ministries and funding organisations across Europe.

The results of the toolkit user requirements survey with responses from 24 European social science archives were presented and discussed, together with suggested approaches and content for the toolkit. 22 people attended the two sessions overall, representing a mix of countries at different stages on the development path for social science archives (none, new/emerging, mature). There was strong interest and support for the emerging toolkit together with open discussion of how it can be applied in the specific political and administrative context of different European countries.

Summary of the Trust Sessions (T4.3)

In total there were three sessions on trust. The first one was the plenary session for all participants of the workshop. This session consisted of a general introduction of trust issue, an introduction into the basics of the new “Common Requirements”, and an overview of the changes in the DSA guidelines by the members of the CESSDA Trust Support Working Group. The main outcome here is that new guidelines contain mostly the same elements as the old ones, but differently organised and presented. Also the problems around the relation between these guidelines and the Annex 2 Obligations were touched upon. In the last part of this session all participants were invited to raise all the points and questions they possibly have on trust. Many service providers stressed their uncertain future and funding which could make it virtually impossible to become DSA-compliant within a year, as the SaW project prescribes. In the second session the timescale and procedure for the DSA-compliance to be reached in a year time was set out. Three categories of SP’s could be distinguished: already certified, more or less close to certification, and starting from beginning. Support both from the Trust Working Group and from certified SPs was much appreciated. It was decided to arrange a common space (CESSDA Basecamp) where all SP’s working on certification could share their provisional results as well as questions and comments. In the last session the new guidelines were discussed in more detail in smaller groups. Out of their experience with the DSA, the members of the Trust Working Group could go into many of the potential problems and tried to clarify a number of the issues. Both the second and the third sessions were well attended, indicating that most SP’s take the trust issue seriously. The discussions and work on trust will be continued, aimed at achieving DSA-certification within a year by as many of the present SPs as possible.

Summary of the Widening CESSDA sessions (T4.5)

Three sessions were organised within task 4.5 aiming at Widening of CESSDA: the first one was a plenary session for all participants of the workshop; the second and third were organised as parallel sessions. There were two main aims of these sessions: to start the developing of the network of collaboration and for collection of information related to “establishing formal mechanisms of collaboration” within this wider CESSDA network. Second goal endorsed a scenario-building approach aimed to identify stakeholders and strategies for the main goal – successful integration in CESSDA or finding other possibilities to build a close collaboration with the CESSDA ERIC.

The plenary session had two parts: at the beginning of the session the partners in the task held several presentations about about CESSDA and its membership: the review of the CESSDA ERIC requirements, the process of joining CESSDA, and needs on the way to become a CESSDA Service Provider. The last presentation gave a summary about the benefits of CESSDA membership. After these presentation the floor was opened for discussions. The discussion was continued during the parallel sessions. Originally, the aim of the third session was to finalise the programme for the WS2 in October in Budapest. However, the programme was previously finalised, and it was reviewed by the participants of the session.

Finally, important conclusions were provided by Tamas Rudas from Tarki Foundation:

- Network of non-member countries' data archives was established during the WS1 in The Hague, as stated in the DOA;
- Funding of non-member countries' archives can be provided by participation in EU funded projects coordinated by CESSDA (e.g. the CESSDA SaW project);
- Recognition issue; decision makers should in respective non-member countries be informed about CESSDA. Proposal for exploring the possibility of MoU with the SPs from the non-member countries (but active in CESSDA) should be presented to the CESSDA Board of Directors in due time;
- Possible cooperation among SPs in CESSDA and outside CESSDA is initiated;
- Possible cooperation between non-member countries' archives.

Summary on Identifying demand for support sessions (T4.4)

The aim of the workshop and the following task meeting was:

1. to Identify needs from partner institutions for development support service;
2. to identify possible provider institutions for development support services;
3. to identify possible pilots of service provider to service provider development support services.

It was not the ambition of this workshop or of task 4.4 to create an exhaustive list of possible development support services or to identify all the needs of all service providers for such services, since not all service providers or aspiring service providers were present at the workshop. Therefore, the approach of aiding service providers was taken thus enabling them to identify both their strengths and areas of need for support services. Three key activities were used:

1. A Wall of Wonder on which participants identified 4 strengths of their institution which were then presented.
2. Speed dating on services they need or could provide between two institutions.
3. A group discussion on areas of need.

Although it was impossible to complete all activities, the whole exercise was considered very beneficial for participants since they communicated and exchanged views with other participants they would not normally communicate with, leading to better understanding of the challenges faced by the community of service providers/data archives as a whole.

This session identified both possible services to be delivered over time and specific activities provided discretely on separate occasions rather than over time. The main technical support service that was of interest was Dataverse, but OAI-PMH server, archival software (FORBase) and back-up services were also discussed. Most of the interest in the final session centred around support activities such as expertise and in particular internships or site visits to other SPs, and perhaps with specific expertise support. Advocacy expertise was also discussed and offered.

In the post-workshop task meeting it has been agreed to pursue the follow pilots:

- Dataverse pilot (lead by DANS) with possible involvement of NSD, IEN, TARKI Foundation, FFZG, ADP, and interest from SODA but they are already running Dataverse.
- CSDA & TARKI will investigate data back-up as a service provision between institutions across borders.
- FSD will offer OAI-PMH server software, but as it was not a technical audience we may need to still find institutions who would like to try it out
- Providing internships as well as a pilot of an expertise support activity, but the number and details are yet to be defined.

3.2. FIGURES ON INVITATIONS AND ATTENDEES

To determine whether the workshop met its goals, a summary of some basic figures from the outcome of the event will be now considered.

- Target audience

Out of a total of 37 potential countries, SPs from 22 countries were actually invited and 20 attended³; two of the invited countries that did not attend were Denmark and Germany.

Figure 5: Map of Invited Countries

When detailing the list of attendees, it is possible to identify participation of people per institution, and whether or not the WS achieved its goal in terms of target audience. As we can see below on the table “people per institution”, 24 institutions attended, all of them sending between one and two representatives. Participation was rather strong since almost all institutions invited took part, ensuring information on DSA certification was spread amongst members of the consortium and even beyond the consortium.

Table 6: People per Institution

People per institution					
Institution	1	2	3	4	5
DANS	1	1			
CESSDA AS	1	1			
Charles Beagrie Ltd	1	1			
CSDA	1	1			
EKKE	1	1			

³ Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Zagreb					
FSD					
ICS-ULisboa/APIs					
IES Serbia					
NSD					
PROGEDO					
SND					
Social Science Data Archives					
TARKI					
UniData - Bicocca Data Archive					
ESSDA					
FORS					
GESIS					
LIDA					
RODA					
Slovak Archive of Social Data					
UK Data Service					
University College Dublin					
Vrije Universiteit Brussel					

The workshop was meant to strengthen existing CESSDA members by providing training on DSA certification and also offered training to aspiring members. Regarding attendance of the event per country, the attendees were mainly CESSDA partners, however only 23 persons out of the 42 were actually CESSDA members. This reflects high participation and provides insight into networking above and beyond actual membership, which is precisely one of the goals of the WS in respect of the WS that will be held in Budapest in M15. Furthermore, one of the sessions was dedicated to preliminary setup of WS2 and attracting attendance from non CESSDA members.

Table 7: Number of Attendees per CESSDA member represented

Number of attendees per CESSDA member represented					
Institution	1	2	3	4	5
DANS ⁴					
CESSDA AS					
CSDA					
FSD					
NSD					
PROGEDO					
SND					
Social Science Data Archives					
FORS					
GESIS					
LiDA					
UK Data Service					

⁴ The overrepresentation of DANS is of course related to the fact that institution was hosting the event.

● Staff attending per role and gender balance

Even though the main target audience of WS1 was technical staff, the table below enables comparison of attendees' profiles originally enrolled to attend the event. Within the registration form, people registering were asked to specify what type of position they held in their institution.

The variety of positions represented amongst attendees is reflected in the diagram below. Relative variations amongst attendees can be noticed regarding the positions they hold within their infrastructure, showing that technical staff category was the least represented category. Data experts were those who were the most represented within the assembly, followed by people occupying strategic, business or data management positions in a SP.

Figure 6: Diagram of Variety of positions represented amongst attendees

These figures are relative depending on the size of particular archives where staff is limited and same person may occupy several positions. Attendees were able to declare several positions, so the occupation of different roles can affect the final results up to some extent. Category "Other" also plays a role in this dynamic overview, since attendees clicking this box were unable to recognize their position in the given fields (see table below).

Figure 7: Number of participant for each category

Since the WS1 was not exclusively aiming at technical staff, it is not surprising to see different profiles attending the event. Analysis of attendees in WS1 also reflects the participation of junior staff recently hired and/or with no prior experience in archiving, thus showing that some archives are relatively small and they do not always have technical staff within their institution.

When examining roles of attendees within SPs, it is interesting to review one of the European Commission regulations. Guidelines push forward the need to respect gender balance when organising activities within EU projects, and that is demonstrated in the table below. Men are overrepresented regardless of their role within infrastructures. The lack of a balanced gender representation may also lead to conclusions about the staff recruitments within the field of archiving.

Figure 8: Attendee gender balance per role

FIGURE 8 - ATTENDEE GENDER BALANCE PER ROLE

● Attendees’ interest for each session and overall aim of the workshop

The last aspect to consider are the sessions that attendees were taking part in. The registration form required from attendees to choose the sessions they would like to attend. Based on the diagram below, all four topics received an equal amount of attention, thus confirming the well balanced programme offered during this workshop and high interest in all topics.

Figure 9: Attendees interest for each session

4. CONCLUSION

The CESSDA-SaW H2020 project aims at achieving full European coverage; the widened membership must form a strong network where global best practice is built into the infrastructure of European social science and research. A series of workshops and conferences taking place during the two year project are being organised to pursue that goal.

This deliverable reported on the process of organising workshops in general and detailed the outcomes of preparation and the main features of WS1. Even though T2.3 was initially designed to provide organisational support to organisers, many issues along with the distribution of events had to be addressed before focusing on the organisation of workshops. Therefore the first section of this report described these issues as well as the way they were addressed in order to provide insight on the present layout of workshops, their inherent logic related to target audiences and deliverables. The first part thus explicits how WS1 was tailored through this process.

D2.3 describes the organisation of the first of the 4 CESSDA SaW workshops and 1 final dissemination event: two are meant to strengthen the network through knowledge exchange between current and aspiring CESSDA Service Providers (SPs), two are aimed at widening the consortium via networking activities bringing together national ministries, Services Providers, Research Councils, and potentially the Social Sciences research community.

As noted previously, the primary intention of WS1 was to train technical staff of CESSDA Service Providers and to assist them in obtaining the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) certification. The DSA Approval is an evaluation and an endorsement from an independent authority capable of demonstrating to users and funders the trustworthiness of data repositories. Other topics were also examined during the event, covering areas promoting partnerships, prospecting sustainability opportunities through support services, and testing a cost/benefit advocacy programme. The target audience originally restricted to technical staff from SPs was broadened bringing together data management and domain experts, as well as business people rather than only technical staff. The overall attendance from almost all SPs in addition to aspiring countries demonstrates that this first step was successful in bringing in new and aspiring members, while still strengthening the skills of current and SPs .

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